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FUTURE CIVIL SERVANTS' BUSINESS ETIQUETTE DEVELOPMENT AS A PART OF PROFESSIONAL IMAGE

РОЗВИТОК ДІЛОВОГО ЕТИКЕТУ МАЙБУТНІХ ДЕРЖАВНИХ СЛУЖБОВЦІВ ЯК СКЛАДОВОЇ ПРОФЕСІЙНОГО ІМІДЖУ

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Гусаріна Н.В., Шепель М.Є., Савченко Д. О. Розвиток ділового етикету майбутніх державних службовців як складової професійного іміджу. Науково-методична стаття.

Стаття присвячена важливості розвитку ділового етикету майбутніх державних службовців як складової їх професійного іміджу. Метою статті виступило визначити роль розвитку ділового етикету майбутніх державних службовців як складової професійного іміджу. У статті розглянуто погляди науковців щодо питань іміджу, професійного іміджу та ділового етикету. Зазначено, що діловий етикет стосується не тільки норм та правил поведінки, поваги до оточуючих, але й культури мовлення. Важливого значення у розвитку ділового етикету майбутніх державних службовців набувають навчальні дисципліни загальної та професійної підготовки, де особливе місце відводиться дисципліні «Імідж та етика в публічному управлінні». Автори зауважують, що крім лекційних та практичних занять важливу роль відіграють самостійна робота здобувачів, участь здобувачів у студентських наукових конференціях, зустріч з публічними діячами (депутатами, заступниками мерів та голів ТГ), робота куратора академічної групи.

Ключові слова: майбутній державний службовець, імідж, професійний імідж, діловий етикет, заклад вищої освіти

Husarina N.V., Shepel M.Ye., Savchenko D. Future Civil Servants' Business Etiquette Development as a Part of Professional Image. Scientific and methodical article.

The article deals with the importance of future civil servants' business etiquette development as a component of their professional image. The aim of the article was to determine the role of future civil servants' business etiquette development as a part of professional image. The article examines the scholars' viewpoints on image, professional image and business etiquette. It has been noted that business etiquette concerns not only the norms and rules of behaviour, respect for others, but also speech culture. The courses of general and professional training are of great importance for the future civil servants' of business etiquette development, where a special place is given to the course "Image and Ethics in Public Administration". The authors note that in addition to lectures and practical classes, the students' independent work, the students' participation in scientific conferences, meeting with public figures (deputies, deputy mayors and territorial communities chairmen), the work of the academic group supervisor play and important role in future civil servants' business etiquette development.

Keywords: future civil servant, image, professional image, business etiquette, a higher education institution

The development of Ukraine as a democratic state, which defends its independence because of the Russia Federation's military aggression puts forward new requirements for specialists' vocational training. But the highest priority in future specialists' training remains a competitive specialist development. The Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education" states that "the educational process is intellectual, creative activity in the sphere of higher education and science, which is carried out at a higher education institution (scientific institution) through the system of scientific, methodical, and pedagogical measures, and is aimed at transferring, mastering, applying and using knowledge, skills and other competencies among people, who are taught, as well as on forming a harmonious developed personality" [1]. Thus, it is important to train a highly competitive specialist who will apply professional knowledge and skills of interpersonal interaction. The labour market of Ukraine presents a wide range of in economic, technical, technological, pedagogical and humanitarian majors. In modern conditions future civil servants' professional training who will represent their communities both in Ukraine and abroad is becoming urgent. A civil servant's behaviour regardless of which type of civil service belongs to his post, his attitude to the profession, to the citizens, his language, appearance create not only his own authority, but also the service authority he represents and the state. The future civil servants' business etiquette development as a component of professional image becomes urgent in the educational process at university.

Analysis of recent research and publications

Both Ukrainian and foreign scientists dedicated their studies to the issues of ethics M. Byram, H. Byrnes, J. Citrion, J. Damen, L. Rudenko; professional business etiquette: K. Hirniak, H. Krasnitska, N. Iovkhimchuk, Ye. Sydorovska, L. Serhieieva, Yu. Matvieieva, O. Konopatska, I. Bostan, C. Costuleanu, E. Horomnea, M. Costuleanu, C.L. Donoho, M.J. Polonsky, S. Roberts, D.A. Cohen, E. Kaynak, N. Delener, O. Lapuzina, R.J. Major, B. Menguc, V.B. Nunes & L.L. de Souza, D. Probuca, N.Y.M. Siu, K.C.J. Lam, A.A. Vásquez-Párraga, A. Kara; M. Ohrenich, N. Iovkhimchuk, K. Goebel, A. Helmke, A.O. Hadley, C. Kramch, P. Parrish, J.A. Linder-VanBershot, S. Rathje, H. Seelye, Zh. Zhogou devoted their researches to speech etiquette; N. Barna, L. Danylchuk, I. Kolosovska, S. Kolosok, Yu. Padafet, O. Gaivoronskaya, O. Kapustyuk, I. Krynicky, O. Myttseva, G. Popova, L. Serhieieva, S. Conway, L. Dobelli, J. Hickey devoted their studies to the issue of image in general and civil servants' image in particular; S. Alaghmand, F. Mozaffar, S.B. Hosseini, B.S. Sedghpour, S. Amelina, H. Yavorska, R. Happ, O. Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia, M. Förster, L. Honebau Vacarescu, G. Săvoiu, C. Necşulescu, M. Ţaicu, L. Şerbănescu, E. Crişan regarded the issues of specialists' professional training and professional becoming.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The conducted analysis of publications and curricula has revealed that business etiquette formation as a component of future specialists' image, in our case civil servants, was not the subject of a special study, which led to the choice of the topic of this article.

The aim of the article is to define the role of future civil servants' business etiquette development as a component of professional image.

The main part

According to the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service", a civil servant is a citizen of Ukraine who holds a civil service position in a public authority, other public authority, its staff (secretariat) (hereinafter – the public authority), receives a salary from the state budget and exercises the powers established for this position, directly related to the

performance of tasks and functions of such public authority, as well as adheres to the civil service principles [2]. As we can see, the issue of future civil servants' business etiquette development is of great importance.

Reference literature considers the concept of image as an opinion that people have about someone or something, which may not be a true one; the opinion of oneself, one's company or one's community that a person deliberately tries to create in the minds of other people [3].

Image belongs to a group of social and psychological phenomena, and therefore, is subject to all the basic laws of social psychology. Among the most important are the following:

- a person being social, is highly dependent on his/her group of social environment; the person's behaviour in the group is determined by stereotypes, generalized and simplified concepts;
- the whole group's attitude to a particular person significantly influences how he/she will be perceived by individual participants;
- in different groups, the same person may have different reputations, and thus the respective behaviour;
- the positive attitude of the group to the individual person contributes to the solution of his/her tasks [4, p. 19].

Considering the civil servant's image except for external elements (business suit, appropriate hairstyle and make-up, smell) it is necessary to take into account that important skills are to enter any social environment, to reduce shortcomings and to highlight their best business qualities. There is an international standard of the civil service representative, its basis is the following: one's own exclusivity and confidence demonstration; one's own satisfaction of life, environment; the winner and successful person's behaviour [5].

The researcher I. Krynychna defines the civil servant's image as consciously formed image of the state power in its personal dimension. From the position of adequacy one distinguishes the following types of image (Figure 1).

The important components of the civil servant's image are professionalism, an organization's psychological climate, management culture. Let's consider them in more detail in the table.

Figure 1. The Types of the Civil Servant's Image

Source: authors' own development

Table 1. The Civil Servant's Image Components

Component	Description
Professionalism	the civil servant's ability to determine the most effective ways and means of tasks realization assigned to them within the limits of the normative defined powers taking into account the conditions and real possibilities
an organization's psychological climate	a labour group's (personnel) mood, its relatively stable mental condition, which reflects the peculiarities of its life, moral atmosphere and relations between employees in the group
management culture	the ability to work competently, professionally, initiatively

Source: authors' own development

In our opinion, another component of the civil servants' image is business etiquette. At the same time, it is connected with professionalism, the organization's psychological climate and corporate culture.

In the framework of our research, the definitions of the terms "ethics" and "etiquette" are of great importance.

Reference literature defines "ethics" as the discipline dealing with what is "good and bad" and with moral duty and obligation. Also ethics is defined as the system of moral principles, aspects [7]. Etiquette is the set of rules or customs that control accepted behaviour in particular social groups social situations [8].

In the concept of business ethics and business etiquette scientists has come to the following conclusions.

I. Bostan, C. Costuleanu, E. Horromnea and M. Costuleanu emphasise that the expression "business ethics" focuses every good, equitable, correct and true element that is present in the assembly of institutions, transactions or efforts, called businesses in general [9, p. 49]. According to O. Bratkova the professional ethics is first and foremost a specific ethics code for people of a particular profession. Each profession puts forward appropriate moral requirements to the people who have chosen it, and it creates particular moral problems [10, p. 89]. The scholar highlights the basic moral and ethical norms that promote effective professional interaction and communication. These norms are integrity, honesty, objectivity, tolerance, respect, responsibility etc. [10, p. 90].

O. Turcu, A. Feraru point out that etiquette requires that a businessman's moral standards should correspond to his behaviour. It regulates the external forms of behaviour, imposing a person's behavioural model [11].

C. Nicolau, K. Alsati and A. Hertanu emphasize that business etiquette can be defined as a specific business style of action with all different people in business, considering their position or origin, whereas a certain kind, using specialized vocabulary, coordination in speech, healthy logic/thinking, straight-forward and direct language, clear communication, consistency, physical purity, etc. [12].

H. Krasnitska highlights the following business etiquette requirements: impeccable appearance, which provides a representative perception of a business person and is a sign of respect for others; speech

culture; verbal and non-verbal communication [13, p. 148].

Considering business etiquette in human resources management K. Hyniak emphasizes that using modern business etiquette norms and rules is based on the following principles: humanism and humanity (are manifested in the requirements to be polite, talented, kind, modest and accurate); expediency (according to which the etiquette gives a person the opportunity to behave reasonably, simply and conveniently for himself and the environment); ethical attractiveness of behaviour; respect for a given organization's traditions and customs [14, p. 63].

Ye. Sergeeva defines the civil servant's official (business) etiquette as a combination of the most appropriate rules of behavior, which improve relations between people in the process of their professional cooperation aimed at fulfillment of tasks and functions of the state [5].

The basis of the civil servant's etiquette are the general principles, which are observed all over the world: humanism, actions expediency, esthetic appeal of behaviour and respect to countries' traditions, with representatives of which the civil servant has to enter into business professional contacts. In addition, the civil servant's business etiquette rules should be based on the following principles:

- friedliness and affability;
- punctuality;
- attention to others, which should apply not only to managers and employees, but also to management services consumers;
- privacy (not to mention unnecessary);
- culture of business communication and literacy.

In our opinion, teaching future civil servants' business speech etiquette while while vocational training is of great importance. It is known that the civil servant's work is associated with constant communication with the leadership and representatives of communities, with representatives of other cities and countries.

Speech (or language) etiquette refers to an accepted set of requirements of forms, contents, orders, characters and situational relevance of utterance or expression. Language etiquette relates to words and phrases that are used for greetings, asking for permission, asking something, addressing someone, giving proper intonation when expressing politeness, etc. [15].

Speech culture requires a speaker to make the right, appropriate choice of language units that would

be appropriate to a particular communicative situation, meet all its parameters. But if the speaker has a limited vocabulary and he constantly repeats the same words, uses them in unusual contexts and situations, overpowers dialectisms, colloquial words, surzhik, if his speech is syntactically monotonous, he cannot hope that he will be considered an interesting interlocutor, a highly cultured or just an educated person [16, p. 72].

Exploring the national and cultural specificity of Ukrainian and English language etiquette the scientist M. Ogrenich notes that there are many similar points in the culture of business communication in both languages. At the same time, there are national features of speech etiquette, characterized by a set of standard clichés of business communication in each language, etiquette formulae for starting, conducting, maintaining, ending a business conversation, telephone clichés etc. They are used by native speakers only in professional communication related to the performance of official duties, normative rules of verbal and non-verbal behaviour in the field of business communication [17, p. 135].

Taking into account the scholars' viewpoints on business etiquette, we can determine that business etiquette concerns not only the norms and rules of conduct, respect for others, but also the speech culture.

Any specialist's business etiquette skills development, in our case, the civil servant should begin from the first days at university. The courses of general and professional training are becoming important.

In our opinion, the course "Image and Ethics in Public Administration" plays a significant role in the future civil servants' business etiquette development.

The aim of the course is to reveal the nature, essence and basic principles of business ethics, to form knowledge about the image of a business person and his role in establishing optimal interaction with business partners, to form an idea of effective means of their own business image development. According to the educational programme "Public Administration" for Bachelor degree, in the process of studying the course "Image and Ethics in Public Administration" students receive the following competencies (general, special) and learning outcomes (Table 2).

As we can see, competences and learning outcomes are aimed at the future civil servants' business etiquette development as a component of professional image.

In order to obtain the programme learning outcomes, the topics for lectures and practical classes were developed (Table 3).

In the process of teaching the course the following methods are used: explanatory and illustrative, problem-solving, time-searching, research methods, conversation and educational discussion.

Applicants's independent work plays a crucial role in preparation for lectures and practical classes, when they learn to work with different sources of information, to separate the truth from the fake.

During the independent work the students are given the task to explore a particular problem, to compare phenomena, to prepare a public speech and presentation, to express their own opinion on a particular problem.

Table 2 Competences and Learning Outcomes, that Gain Students after Finishing the Course

The competence name	The competence component
Integral competence	The ability to solve complex specialized tasks and practical problems in the field of public administration or in the learning process, which involves theories and scientific methods application of a particular area and is characterized by complexity and uncertainty of conditions
GC 12. Interpersonal skills	LO 7. To be able to organize and participate in volunteer / cultural, educational / sports projects aimed at forming a healthy lifestyle / active citizenship LO 12. To be able to establish communication between citizens and public authorities and local self-government bodies
SC 1. Ability to social interaction, cooperation and conflict resolution	LO 7. To be able to organize and participate in volunteer / cultural, educational / sports projects aimed at forming a healthy lifestyle / active citizenship LO 11. To be able to search and summarize information, draw conclusions and formulate recommendations within one's own competence. LO 12. To be able to establish communication between citizens and public authorities and local self-government bodies
SC 3. Ability to ensure compliance with regulations -legal and moral and ethical norms of behaviour.	LO 2. To apply norms and rules of professional communication in Ukrainian. LO 5. To know the standards, principles and norms of activity in the field of public administration . LO 6. To know the basic legal acts and statutory instruments in the field of public administration.

Source: authors' own development

Table 3. The Topics for Lectures and Practical Classes

Lectures	Practical Classes
1. The essence of business relations ethics	1. The essence of business relations ethics
2. Image and ethics of organizations' activity	2. Image and ethics of organizations' activity
3. A leader's image and ethics	3. A leader's image and ethics
4. Business communication and its management	4. Business communication and its management
5. Business relations rules	5. Business relations rules
6. Conflicts and their management	6. Conflicts and their nature
7. A business person's etiquette	7. Etiquette of a business person and business relations
8. Professional ethics specifics and issues	
9. Basic principles and norms of ethics of the civil servant's ethics	
10. Ethical principles of the relationship between civil servants and citizens	
11. Ethical aspects of interest conflicts in public administration	
12. Relationships in a civil servant's team	
13. Mechanisms to support civil servants' ethics	

Source: authors' own development

The Covid-19 pandemic and Russia's military aggression against Ukraine have drastically changed the learning paradigm. Professors and students have learned to work online using different platforms. Well, teaching online has its advantages: in the process of lectures and practical classes, professors and students watch videos, which are then discussed; professors and students give presentations and do not need a big screen; group presentations can be created online. But, in our opinion, online communication will never replace the face-to-face one.

In addition to lectures and practical classes, students' scientific conferences, meetings with public figures (deputies, deputy mayors and territorial communities chairmen), work of the academic group supervisor are important for future civil servants' business etiquette development.

Thus, during taking part in a conference a student speak in public with his/her presentation and answers the audience's questions adhering to the business speech etiquette rules. In the process of meeting with public figures, which often takes the form of a

discussion, the students ask questions about their future professional activities following the rules of business etiquette. An academic group supervisor plays an important role in future civil servants' business etiquette development. It is the academic group supervisor who holds a conversation with the group about the norms and rules behaviour, culture in public places and in the street.

Conclusions

Thus, as we see, the future civil servants' business etiquette development of as a component of image is a complex and multifaceted process. In this process, it is important to combine the study of general and professional courses with the students' participation in scientific conferences, meetings with public figures (deputies, deputy mayors and amalgamated territorial communities chairmen), the academic groups supervisors' work. Further study becomes the problem of studying the ethical principles of the relationship between civil servants and citizens.

Abstract

The development of Ukraine as a democratic state, which defends its independence because of Russia's military aggression puts forward new requirements for specialists' vocational training. But the highest priority in future specialists' training remains a competitive specialist development. We should train a highly competitive specialist who will be able to apply professional knowledge and skills of interpersonal interaction. In modern conditions future civil servants' professional training who will represent their communities both in Ukraine abroad, is becoming important. Future civil servants' business etiquette development as a component of professional image becomes urgent in the educational process at universities. Both Ukrainian and foreign scientists dedicated their works to issues of ethics, professional business etiquette, speech etiquette, issues of image in general and civil servants' image in particular, specialists' professional training and professional becoming.

The aim of the article was to define the role of future civil servants' business etiquette development as a component of professional image.

The important components of the civil servant's image are professionalism, an organization's psychological climate, management culture and business etiquette. We can say that business etiquette concerns not only the norms and rules of conduct, respect for others, but also the speech culture.

In the process of future civil servants' business etiquette development it is important to combine the study of general and professional courses with the students' participation in scientific conferences, meetings with public figures (deputies, deputy mayors and territorial communities chairmen), the academic groups supervisors' work.

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